

Creating a learning style map for English as a foreign language student to discover effective study methods

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ABSTRACT

This research determines the student's learning strategies based on their learning styles. This research applied qualitative study. The subject of this research is the students of English literature class A in Universitas Negeri Makassar, who were selected through a purposive sampling technique. Thirty-five students were chosen as the subjects of this study. The data were obtained through questionnaires and interviews and then analyzed based on producers of data analysis identification, classification, and descriptive analysis. The result showed that i) there are some learning styles that students have, such as visual, auditory, and kinesthetic (VAK) learning styles; and ii) students' learning strategies based on their learning style where subjects engaged in several learning activities or methodologies. Two types of learning techniques were primarily considered: individual and group strategies. The individual strategies were marked by all of the activities the subjects had done, and the group strategies described the learning actions employed by the subjects to comprehend the knowledge or the lesson by engaging friends who could help them.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In contrast to their ancestors, modern pedagogical approaches emphasize the students and their learning more than the language and the teachers. Traditionally, students in schools were not taught independent study skills. Conversely, in more contemporary, learner-centered perspectives, the goal is for students to become aware of their learning styles and select the best methods. Consequently, to create a more conducive environment for teaching, it is necessary to consider many factors about the students of the language and their relationship to the course material, delivery method, and assessment tools. Rephrasing, motivating, and expecting students to participate actively in their education is essential. A student's academic success is affected by a variety of personal traits. Littlewood [1] argues that while language development follows a singular trajectory, learners may diverge in their courses due to individual variations. Both learning styles and learning strategies are encompassed within individual differences.

Learning styles refer to individuals' preferred methods of engaging in activities such as thinking, processing, and comprehending information [2], [3]. There is no guarantee that all students will have the same learning style. They go about their education in a variety of methods. They differ in several topological variables [4], [5] or an overwhelming variety of theories on the many ways in which students learn [6]. Learning styles are formed by a combination of a person's personality, intelligence, and other fixed features;

these and other significant notions come from well-established theories in psychology [7]. Numerous academics in psychology and education have focused on learning styles, leading to a plethora of competing theories, explanations, and models on the subject. As an example, Dunn and Dunn [8] wrote their definition of learning styles as stated:

“Learning style refers to how individuals focus on, process, assimilate, and remember new and challenging knowledge. These factors interact uniquely in each individual. Hence, it is essential to identify the factors that are most likely to stimulate each student's focus, how to sustain it, and how to adapt to their innate cognitive style to enhance long-term memory and retention. It is crucial to utilize a comprehensive learning style model that may uncover an individual's strengths and preferences in several aspects like physiology, sociology, psychology, emotions, and surroundings to expose their inherent tendencies and styles.”

Every human person possesses a distinct learning style, and these styles can be categorized as either standard or trademark. Most learning style taxonomies classify them into 'type'. Each theory classifies individuals into purportedly separate categories instead of giving them numerical ratings on several aspects [4], [9]. Some students learn visually, while others learn auditorily or kinesthetically [5], [10]. Visual learners receive and process information visually through charts, graphs, and pictures. Auditory learners learn by using their hearing as a tool for both internal and external communication. Kinesthetic learners gain knowledge by doing. Some students may discover they have more than one or two learning styles [11]. The various learning styles of these students can serve as a reference for lecturers in identifying the range of learning techniques and including activities relevant to each of these learning styles in their curriculum so that all students can succeed in their classes. The prominent idea is that instruction should be provided in a mode that matches the learner's style [9]. For instance, if the learner is a 'visual learner,' information should, when possible, be presented visually. The most effective way for visual learners to activate their vision is through the use of written texts, graphs, or pictures. Kinaesthetic and tactile learners, on the other hand, are most likely to learn effectively if they can touch and handle the objects they are learning with, play motion games, and move around [4].

Students' learning styles define how they take information through their senses and the more dominant ones during learning. According to Dunn [12], several factors support learning styles: environment, emotional, sociological, physiological, and psychological. Furthermore, election strategies appropriate to their styles will benefit them in learning the English language. According to Stern *et al.* [13], the idea of a learning strategy highly depends on the proposition that students would actively participate in classroom activities to accomplish specific objectives established in advance. Research by Griffiths [14] states that learning strategies are a broad concept encompassing purposeful directives and learning procedures. Language learners employ language-learning processes, consciously or unconsciously, to absorb information and carry out tasks.

On the other hand, numerous researchers have detailed successful language learners and the tools at their disposal. A significant finding among these is that successful language learners generally employ a more significant number of and more effective learning strategies than learners with lower proficiency levels. These findings have been observed time and time again in the research on learning strategies for second languages (L2) [14], [15]. Research by Özbaş [2] made an inquiry into the learning preferences of university students. He claimed that roughly 50% of students acquired knowledge through visual means. Through an examination of the impact of gender on students' learning methods, it was discovered that girls consistently achieved significantly higher averages than boys in visual learning. He said that lecturers should be aware of their student's learning styles, intending that teachers understand what they should do during the teaching process in the classroom. Additionally, ensuring that students remain at ease throughout the course is crucial, as it enables them to learn effectively and accomplish commendable results by understanding their learning patterns.

Meanwhile, Lee [16] did an overview of language learning strategies. They mentioned that many researchers have found that several variables, such as age, gender, individual differences, motivation, and cultural background, affect language learning strategies. Also, it provides a point of reference for future studies in the area of language strategies, explicitly illuminating the connection between one's cultural background, the language they are learning, and the application of methods, and guiding us towards the present state of learning strategies and the teaching of learning strategies.

Cabual [5] stated that learning is an ongoing process, and a process is a series of actions that ultimately result in a specific outcome. The learning process might be slowed down or even stopped entirely if there are obstacles to learning. The recognition of the learner's preferred learning mode can result in more efficient learning. He examined Neil Fleming's visual, auditory, and kinesthetic (VAK) learning style models done by students during the new average era. In 2021, for the time being, face-to-face communication is

prohibited because the pandemic is still rampant over the globe. Both students and teachers are required to adjust to the requirements of the new normal. Conventional face-to-face training has been substantially superseded by other means of instruction, such as digital and online delivery modes, mixed or versatile delivery modes, synchronous or asynchronous delivery modes, or a combination of these alternative modes of instruction [17]. Results show that most students utilize the "visual" learning style, while the remaining three learning styles are distributed evenly. Throughout the epidemic, most students opted to purchase the courses in complex form. They can learn at their own pace and in their own time, thanks to the modules that their different teachers provide. Kinesthetic, auditory, and reading/writing abilities are also present.

Students who had various learning strategies would quickly master the materials. Therefore, the success of teaching English to speakers of other languages (also known as EFL) depends on various factors. Students' preference for their preferred learning style was believed to be a significant component among the aspects that have significantly contributed to the success of mastery of several foreign languages [18]. The students' learning style preferences can provide teachers with valuable insight when it comes to controlling activities in the classroom. Certain students may prefer a particular mode of education due to their unique learning patterns. Therefore, the researchers attempt to investigate strategies VAK learners use to learn English. This study investigates students' individual learning style preferences in English literature of Universitas Negeri Makassar and students' language learning strategies. Based on the problem found, the researchers conducted research entitled creating a learning style map for college students to discover effective study methods.

2. METHOD

The researchers used a descriptive qualitative research design to find the answer to the research after Ones. It is primarily an inductive process of organizing data into categorizing and identifying patterns. It also collects data about students' learning strategies based on their learning styles. It described phenomena that occur in the field. The researchers used a questionnaire to collect the data.

Meanwhile, observation and interviews determined students' learning styles and strategies. Gay *et al.* [19] stated that qualitative research collects, analyzes, and interprets comprehensive narrative and visual data to gain insights into a particular phenomenon of interest. Specifically, it applied explorative study in teaching English as a foreign language (TEFL) since the researcher explored the students' learning styles, learning strategies, and the strategies used by the VAK learners.

This research was conducted at Universitas Negeri Makassar. The participants of this research were English literature students in class A. There were 35 students in the school, consisted 27 females and eight males. The researchers applied the purposive sampling technique to take the participants in this research. Purposive sampling determines the participants by considering something [20]. The researchers chose the subjects of study, applying specific criteria. For selecting subjects of this research who have qualifications such as the subjects were good learners, the recommendation from their lecturers. After that, the researchers discussed with the English literature study program English lecturer at Universitas Negeri Makassar, Indonesia, because they believe they know their students' characteristics well. Therefore, the researchers were easy to analyze the student's learning style and their learning strategies in English activities.

Managing the instrument to collect the data should be seriously handled to obtain accurate results. Therefore, the researcher collected the data using the following tools: questionnaire, observation, and interview. A questionnaire was distributed to find out what learning style students had. Furthermore, a classroom interview was distributed to determine students' learning strategies in a classroom activity. To collect the data, the researchers executed the following procedures: profoundly understanding the studies on relevant topics and preparing a list of written questions related to learning styles. Also, researchers attended the classroom learning and teaching process to gain information about the student's learning styles based on the questionnaires given to the students. After that, the researchers interviewed the students as additional information based on observation results. The Interview session used semistructured interview data about the students' problems based on their learning style. At the end of the research session, the researchers collected the data from a questionnaire and interviewed the data to find answers to the questions.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Students' learning styles

To find their learning styles, students were asked to complete the questionnaire to determine their preferences. This questionnaire consisted of 14 questions delivered by the researchers. Questions 1-4 are referred to the visual, questions 5-8 are referred to auditory, and questions 9-14 are referred to kinesthetic. Scale responses for each question described: never (0), rarely (1), sometimes (2), often (3), always (4). The

following table, which is based on the students' sensory style dimension, has been supplied to demonstrate each learning style on its own and how students replied to each topic in the questionnaire.

The data from Table 1 indicates that some students prefer the visual learning approach. 39.4% of students have improved memory retention when writing while listening, whereas 3.1% do not experience this benefit. 57.6% of students frequently engage in the practice of taking comprehensive notes during lectures. Approximately 36.4% of students seldom engage in mental imagery, whether visualizing pictures, individuals, or words. 42.2% of students occasionally favor learning through television or video over other forms of media. The data presented in Table 1 indicates that students prefer video-based learning over other forms of media.

Table 1. Students visual learning style preference

No	Question item	N (%)	R (%)	S (%)	O (%)	A (%)
1	I have a more enhanced recollection of information when physically recording it in writing.	3.1	6.1	39.4	24.2	27.3
2	During class, I make sure to take thorough notes.	0	6.1	27.3	57.6	9.1
3	My mind comes up with pictures as I listen.	6.1	36.4	21.2	21.2	15.2
4	Video and television are my preferred learning tools.	6.1	24.2	42.4	18.2	9.1

Additionally, students have excellent retention when they engage in the act of writing information down. Furthermore, students refrain from mentally engaging in visualizing images or word associations but frequently take comprehensive notes during lectures. This learning preference is classified as modality, with one of its learner categories being visual learners.

According to Table 2, 33.3% of students prefer to learn by listening to a lecturer rather than reading textbooks. This preference is consistent across all students. 36.4% of pupils can recognize individuals based on their voice. 42.4% of pupils have never been aided in their thinking by background noise. And 39.4% of pupils cannot comprehend what other individuals say, even if they cannot see them. In addition, students can recognize individuals based on their voice and comprehend what others say even if they cannot see them. The findings presented in Table 2 demonstrate that students prefer to learn by listening to a lecturer rather than reading. The learner type included in the modified model is the auditory learner. This learning falls under the modified model.

Table 2. Students auditory learning style preference

No	Question item	N (%)	R (%)	S (%)	O (%)	A (%)
1	I prefer acquiring knowledge through auditory means, such as attending lectures, instead of relying on reading materials.	6.1	6.1	21.2	33.3	33.3
2	Hearing audio in the background helps me think.	42.4	18.2	21.2	18.2	0
3	I can comprehend what others say even when I cannot see them.	27.3	39.4	21.2	24.2	15.2
4	I can recognize someone based on their voice.	6.1	21.2	36.4	24.2	12.1

From the information in Table 3, 30% of students never experience nervousness from sitting for extended periods, while 39.4% think more effectively when they engage in physical movement and require food or drink while learning. Table 3 reveals that students seldom experience anxiety when they remain seated for extended periods. Occasionally, the students have enhanced cognitive abilities when they engage in physical movement. Given the option, they prefer to assume a standing position rather than sitting. This learning preference belongs to the mobility model, precisely the kinesthetic learner type. To support the data above, the researchers also conducted observation by having the observation checklist to study each VAK learning style. Each learning styles show some indicators done by students during the observation. Those indicators are displayed in Table 4.

Table 3. Students' kinesthetic learning style preference

No	Question item	N (%)	R (%)	S (%)	O (%)	A (%)
1	When I am learning, I require food or liquids.	24.2	27.3	30.3	6.1	12.1
2	I prefer to stand if given the option rather than sit.	21.2	24.2	33.3	18.2	3.1
3	Sitting for extended periods makes me anxious.	0	42.4	15.2	15.2	0
4	I am more cognitively adequate when I engage in physical movement.	18.2	15.2	39.4	12.1	15.2

Table 4. Characteristics of subjects' learning styles

No.	Variables	Indicators
1.	Visual learning styles	a. Learning by visual b. Make a note c. Memorize by repeating d. Remember the text e. The eyeball looks upward f. Faster reader g. Have a short answer h. No good at choosing words i. Like drawing/ art/ something related to vision
2.	Auditory learning styles	a. Learning by listening b. Enjoy the discussions c. Talking to himself d. Reading aloud e. eyeball looks to the left or right f. Difficulties in visual work g. Faster speaker h. Spoke with unclear intonation i. Easily distracted by noise j. Like music
3.	Kinesthetic learning styles	a. Learning by doing b. Can not sit for a long time c. Drammed fingers on the table d. Pointing the reading e. The eyeball looking down f. Raise hands for the first time when the teacher gives questions g. Using body language h. Stand close to the interlocutors i. Have a poor writing j. Enjoy physical

Nevertheless, this study identified three distinct learning styles, allowing the researchers to determine the learning type of each student after assessing their scores. The top-performing students refrained from adopting this scoring learning approach, as it did not align with their preferred learning style. Data from questionnaires were then integrated by those indicators shown during the observations. The table displays the learning style of students in English literature at Universitas Negeri Makassar.

Figure 1 illustrates the many learning styles employed in studying English literature. The data was acquired from the questionnaire administered to the pupils. After evaluating students' responses and categorizing their learning styles based on each dimension, it was determined that 23 students exhibited a visual learning style, seven had an auditory learning style, and five had a kinesthetic learning style. The researchers discovered that of the 35 students who participated in the study, 23.66% were classified as visual learners, 7.20% as auditory learners, and 5.14% as kinesthetic learners.

Figure 1. Student's learning styles

3.2. Students' learning strategies

Learning techniques encompass all students' activities to acquire and comprehend knowledge or achieve their learning objectives. They did not just implement these tactics in school but were also employed in all their activities whenever they needed to acquire or understand knowledge. Based on the interview data, the researchers discovered that the subjects employed various learning activities or strategies in this study. The learning strategies were classified into two primary categories: individual and group. Individual

strategies were defined by all of the subjects' actions or activities. In contrast, group strategies described the learning actions taken by the subjects themselves to comprehend the knowledge or lesson by enlisting the help of friends. The Table 5 depicts the identification of activities relevant to the learning strategy.

Table 5. Students' learning strategy-based observation checklist

Students' activities	Checklist	Name of subcategory	
a. Give a sign writing on the piece of paper		Individual strategy	
b. Using synonym			
c. Using body language			
d. Use flashcards/pictures to remember the lesson			
e. Input previous vocabulary or some words that have been memorized in the speaking process			
f. Preparing the lesson for the next day			
g. Have clear goals for learning English			
h. Do the task seriously			
i. Make repetition			
j. Enjoy the learning process			
k. calm and speak slowly			
l. Asking the friend and teacher			Group strategies
m. Practice with a friend			
n. Study/discuss with friends			

From the Table 5, it could be concluded that students implemented individual and group strategies. The individual approach was the strategy used by the subjects without assistance from others. As learners, we must identify the purpose of the learning process. The subjects used some ways to find their goal. The students stated that it was difficult for them to memorize English because it was a foreign language. As a result, students needed to repeat the English class several times to fully understand the topic or lesson they had learned. When they wished to emphasize a lesson or issue that was highly significant to them, they would underline the sentences or topic, as shown in the following statement, which was extracted from interviews with subjects and their friends. Meanwhile, in group strategies, students did not rely solely on themselves to increase their knowledge. They still needed help from their surroundings and friends. They enjoy having discussions. In their group, they attempted to share, discuss, and practice their knowledge with their peers. They consulted their peers or teachers when they needed information, especially during learning.

3.2.1. Students' strategies used by visual, auditory, and kinesthetic (VAK) learners

The subject used combined strategies in learning. Visual learners utilized strategies such as memory, cognitive, compensatory, emotive, and social learning. The auditory learners utilized strategies such as memory, cognitive, compensatory, affective, and social learning. Kinesthetic learners and auditory learners alike share memory, cognitive, compensatory, emotive, and social methods. Kinesthetic learners also use these strategies. The figure of the strategies used by VAK learners is shown in Table 6.

3.2.2. Learning styles

As presented in the research findings above, data were collected from the three students selected as the study subjects. From those data, the researchers knew that the student's learning styles and strategies of English Literature Universitas Negeri Makassar employed more than one learning style and strategy. This study had several findings; the first was that subjects showed a combination of VAK learning styles, and each had one preference. The second subject showed a combination of memory, cognitive, affective, and social learning strategies. They learned in different ways in the learning process.

Based on the first findings, the subjects did not only have one learning style but showed a combination of learning styles. The subject read books, paid great attention to the teacher's explanation, enjoyed the discussion, asked their teacher, and did other activities during the learning process. They memorized the lessons by repeating them; these findings in the result of the observation checklist in Table 6 were the same as Oxford [21], who said that the students have VAK learning styles. The subjects learned through hearing, seeing, writing, touching, and moving. They actively asked questions, enjoyed discussions with their friends/teacher, played drama, did physical activities, and played with their fingers on the table or moved their feet. As stated in the findings, the research subject could not stay on the seat for a long time; it was also proved in the teacher's interview in extract 6.

"IK, dia banyak ngomong dan suka jalan-jalan"
 ("IK, he talked too much and walked around the classroom").

It also suits Wahab and Nuraeni's findings [22] that stated that the students never sit passively, such as hearing or reading only, but are frequently active in various learning activities. The students found their styles and strategies in learning. According to Nunan [23], categorized good language learners he states that a good language learner had some characteristics, they were: i) develop their methods of learning; ii) are imaginative and exploratory in their use of language; iii) create their practice opportunities, both in and out of the classroom; iv) make use of one's understanding of language and linguistics, especially one's native tongue, to become fluent in two languages; v) master the art of educated guesswork; vi) make mistakes work so you can learn and communicate; and vii) have a handle on production techniques. So, students with different learning strategies are qualified to become good language learners [24].

Table 6. Student strategies used by VAK learners

	Visual learners	Auditory learners	Kinesthetic learners
Memory strategies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - I am using flashcards/pictures to remember the lesson/words. - Input the previous vocabulary or some words memorized during the speaking process. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Input the previous vocabulary or some words memorized in the speaking process. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Input the previous vocabulary or some words memorized in the speaking process.
Cognitive strategies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - They give a sign, underline, and color the text on their notebook. - I am doing the task seriously. - I am making repetition. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Making repetition. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - I am making repetition.
Compensation strategies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - I am using synonyms. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Using synonym. - I am using body language. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - I am using synonyms. - I was using body language.
Affective strategies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - I am preparing the lesson for the next day. - Have clear goals for learning English. - Enjoy the learning process. - Calm down and speak slowly. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - I am preparing the lesson for the next day. - Have clear goals for learning English. - Enjoy the learning process. - Calm down and speak slowly. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - I am preparing the lesson for the next day. - Have clear goals for learning English. - Enjoy the learning process. - Calm down and speak slowly.
Social strategies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - I am asking the friend and the teacher. - Practice with friends. - Study/discuss with the friends 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Asking the friend and teacher. - Practice with friends. - Study/discuss with the friends 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - I am asking my friend and teacher. - Practice with friends. - Study/discuss with the friends

3.2.3. Learning strategies

The data was analyzed in the previous section; several learning strategies were also recognized as learning actions performed by the subjects. That learning strategy was based on Oxford's classification [25] in his study "language learning strategy (LLS)". He classified the LLS into two main categories: direct and indirect strategy. The direct strategy is divided into three subcategories: memory, cognitive, and compensation. Indirect strategy is divided into three subcategories: metacognitive, affective, and social. Both of them were majors and subcategories performed by this study's subject. In direct strategy, the subject was responsible for carrying out all of the strategies, whereas in indirect strategy, emotional strategy, and social strategy, the subjects were primarily responsible for carrying out the tactics.

In the memory strategy, the subjects tried to input the previous vocabulary or some words memorized during the speaking process. In a manner comparable to Oxford's classification, inserting some vocabulary or new words and then speaking was a component of building mental links, which involved putting new words into a new context before speaking. The interview with the subject showed that in the learning process, the subjects always tried to use and input some new vocabulary, such as stated. Numerous studies have also proven that embedding new words in context is the best way to memorize a word effectively since the target words and the surrounding words can be acquired. They learned words by heart and then put those words to use in their everyday lives. Due to the fact that they had memorized and exercised the language, they were able to retain it well through the application of this approach. Let us assume that children are able to memorize certain terminology without making any effort to utilize it, repetition, or communicating regularly. It was in line with Tuan's [26] statement that learners forget how to spell words when they had little occasion to use them.

Cognitive strategies, such as repetition, giving a sign, writing in the piece, and practicing English with friends, were the actions performed by the subjects in their learning activities. These strategies were

very joyful for them. Repetition was the action the subjects performed to understand and comprehend something. Because English as a foreign language (EFL), they found some difficulty comprehending the knowledge. Consequently, they were compelled to iterate the lesson/words till they comprehended. Repetition was frequently employed to achieve proficiency in mathematics and memorize sequences of numbers when acquiring a foreign language. Repetition significantly influences how individuals construct and interpret meanings. In this respect, Johnstone [27] argued that repetition created a cognitive effect. They improved their speed of becoming familiar with and comprehending new information through repetition. By the principle of repetition, the subject carried out the activities of giving a sign, writing the essential information or words on a piece of paper or book, and delivering signals. It was recognized as a creating structure for the input and output of the actions, which is part of cognitive strategy. The subject signed the sentences by using colors. Giving signs showed the necessary information/words but also made it easier for them to remember those information/words.

Practicing English with friends is also part of the cognitive strategy. As foreign language learners, practicing the previous knowledge is crucial. The subjects benefited from practice because they could apply knowledge through interaction. When they practice using the knowledge through the application, they connect with information/words on a deeper level. With practicing, it was easier to develop their knowledge. The tactics of pointing and synonym use are employed to address any limits or unfamiliar phrases that may arise throughout the talk. Gestures either emphasize spoken words or express feelings and emotions [28].

After explaining the strategies performed by the subjects in their learning activities in terms of direct strategies, it is time to explain the indirect strategies found during this study. In this study, the subjects performed two subcategories of indirect strategy; those actions were affective and social strategy. The three sets of methods the subjects utilized in their learning approaches were self-encouragement, being calm and speaking slowly, and feeling excellent in English. These are all examples of effective tactics. As they went through the process of learning, they found that turning to be calm and speaking slowly were effective ways to minimize their fear. Feeling good in English is also included in an effective strategy. The essential aspects that must exist in the English classroom are enjoying the classroom situation, enjoying the learning process, and not being under pressure. This effectively aids the subjects in lowering their anxiety [29]. The subjects implemented various actions in their social strategy. They actively pursue opportunities to apply their knowledge and immerse themselves in the target language, such as engaging in study sessions with peers, seeking guidance from friends and teachers, and engaging in discussions with friends, such as stated:

“Saya lebih suka belajar dengan cara berdiskusi dengan teman-teman. Jadi, dengan berdiskusi kami bisa bertukar informasi, dan belajarnya juga tidak membosankan”.

(I preferred to study by discussing with friends. We could share information by discussing things with friends, and the study was exciting).

It is a crucial component of social strategy. Social dynamics arise from the reciprocal interaction between individuals and their shared environment, where one person's actions influence another, and the subsequent reaction of the second person influences the first person once more. Social contact facilitates the exchange of information among individuals, allowing them to coordinate their efforts and engage in cooperation effectively. In addition, forming interpersonal relationships is essential [30], as it builds relationships with and among students [31]. The actions of the subjects are similar to Oxford's taxonomy. According to Oxford, three sets of strategies are included in social strategies: asking questions, cooperating, and emphasizing with others. It is a fact that asking questions cannot be separated from our lives [32]. The more we question, the more we get. When the subject faced difficulties getting the necessary knowledge, they would try to find some information/words from the people who could help them. For example, in the classroom, they would ask the lecturer, and they could get what the lecturer meant to convey.

Teachers are aware of how a range of students employ different learning styles because students have a variety of learning styles, and the diverse learning styles impact learning and academic accomplishment [33]. Learning can be defined as the process of accepting and processing knowledge, which occurs in various persons in the same way. Teachers who work with students with varying learning styles must acknowledge that each student may have a unique approach to completing their assignments and acquiring the most recent information regularly. As a result, teachers need to be ready to cope with any learning style their students may have. Riad *et al.* [34] even added that customizing the learning process has several important purposes, one of which is to provide students with consistent surroundings that take into consideration their specific preferences and interests in learning. Even educators may view learning style assessments as an appealing method for implementing what they consider evidence-based practice in the classroom. The multitude of existing measures broadly claim to provide evidence of characteristics and

tendencies related to learning, and as a bonus, they come with step-by-step instructions [6]. Thus, it is of the utmost importance to develop a student-specific learning environment that is capable of adapting to the learners' preferred mode of learning and intelligently recommending learning items to enhance the learning process since an individual's cognitive and psychological abilities to respond to their learning environment and interactions are linked to their learning style.

4. CONCLUSION

Based on the result of the research, it was found that the students of English literature class use various learning styles and learning strategies in learning. They chose their learning styles based on their characteristics, creativity, and interests. The findings indicate that three learning style models belong to students of English literature at Universitas Negeri Makassar. The first is the modality model, consisting of the VAK styling style thesis. 9.1% of students indicated they are visual learners, and 3.03% of students indicated they are auditory and kinesthetic learners. The second model is the personality model, which consists of extroverts and introverts. Based on the data obtained from the questionnaire, 36.4% of students are indicated as extrovert learners (the highest percentage of learning style), and 24.2% are indicated as introvert. The third is the receiving information model, which consists of global and analytical learning styles. 3.03% of students are indicated as global learners, and 21.2% of students are indicated as analytical learners. The data found that students have different learning styles.

Observation and interviews conducted by the researchers found that students showed some learning strategies. The subjects also showed a combination of learning strategies. The learning strategies they used were memory, cognitive, compensation, affective, and social strategies. The researcher understood that all those learning strategies were helpful for the students. By using those strategies, they could be good language learners. Consequently, they could learn the language successfully. VAK learners used all those strategies in learning English, although they had different learning methods. So, those strategies are essential for language learners.

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